

Exploring the Impact of RDM Across Domains

Tales from the NFDI4DS Speedboat Projects

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Introduction to NFDI4DS Speedboat Projects

The National Research Data Infrastructures for Data Science and Artificial Intelligence (NFDI4DS) consortium [1] has been supporting efforts to collect and manage research data for the development of Data Science (DS) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) in diverse domains. These Speedboat Projects have been supported financially and methodologically by NFDI4DS. In the following, we provide an overview of the currently running Speedboat Projects as case studies for the utility and impact of the research data management (RDM) services offered by the consortium and indicate vice versa how they help us to fulfill our mission.

RDM in Action: A Closer Look at the Speedboat Projects

ChildLens: Childhood Development Research with Video Data

Authors: Nele Suffo & Manuel Bohn

ChildLens is an audio-visual dataset that was collected by developmental psychologists for the development of computer vision, speech, and multimodal machine learning technology. The dataset consists of recordings of children aged 3 to 5 in their natural home environment, taken from a first-person viewpoint, and includes manual annotations for a broad range of activity classes, such as talking, book reading, and playing. The dataset fills a crucial gap in efforts to study children's daily activities on a large scale. The sensitive nature of the data poses special RDM challenges. To ensure that it is used only for research purpose and prevent misuse, the dataset is made available through the website of the Max Planck Institute for evolutionary Anthropology.¹ Access is only possible upon request and compliance with strict privacy requirements. Each request will be manually reviewed by the responsible researcher. This project helps NFDI4DS take its first step into the computer vision and psychology domains.

¹<https://www.eva.mpg.de/comparative-cultural-psychology/technical-development/childlens/>

Automated Systematic Literature Reviews

Authors: Charlotte Gohr & Henrick von Wehrden

This project focuses on the development of tools for the automated screening, categorizing, and analysis of scientific articles across disciplines. The multivariate statistics analysis for scientific literature is developed and published as an R package, which will be made publicly available. The package will be registered via the Open Research Knowledge Graph (ORKG),² which will allow cataloging the package with rich metadata, according to FAIR standards. Within the project, add-ons are developed to integrate supervised machine learning for bibliometric data extraction. The outcomes are applied to exemplary in-house (Leuphana) published scientific literature reviews. This speedboat aids the purpose of NFDI4DS to take better care of information science and to speed up research over RDM itself.

Generation of synthetic expert-validated electronic health records datasets

Author: Daniel Schneider

The objective of this speedboat project is to generate realistic synthetic electronic health record (EHR) datasets, like a handful of large-scale publicly available datasets, which are primarily focused on intensive care unit (ICU) data. This initiative addresses the limited access to real EHRs due to privacy concerns by leveraging large language models to create artificial records. These synthetic records will undergo rigorous expert evaluation by medical professionals to ensure clinical accuracy and identify potential issues. The project's goals include developing a benchmark dataset comprising at least 500 expert-validated synthetic ICU patient timelines. Plans are in place to expand this dataset to 10,000 records, leveraging insights derived from the validation process. This synthetic data will be used as an undisclosed test set for medical AI competitions, thereby fostering the development of trustworthy and explainable AI systems for healthcare applications.

Annotating ClimateCheck: A Dataset of Social Media Claims About Climate Change Evidenced by Scholarly Papers

Authors: Raia Abu Ahmad & Georg Rehm

The core objective of this endeavor is to advance evidence-based policymaking and deepen public understanding of climate change. To achieve this, the initiative employs a structured approach: first, relevant social media posts and scholarly publications are collected. Subsequently, claims from these posts are automatically linked to corresponding publications [2]–[4]. These linkages are then categorized into three groups—support, refute, or insufficient evidence—utilizing open-source large language models (LLMs). Following this classification, environmental science experts undertake a manual review of the dataset to ensure accuracy. The refined dataset will eventually be released for the shared task under the ClimateCheck challenge,³ aiming to foster innovation and enhance understanding in addressing climate change. Thus, this speedboat helps set a foot in the sustainability sciences, which require novel data science and AI techniques due to their composite nature over heterogeneous data.

²<https://orkg.org/>

³<https://www.codabench.org/competitions/6639/>

SciVQA: Scientific Visual Question Answering

Authors: Ekaterina Borisova & Georg Rehm

SciVQA is a new dataset aimed at advancing visual question answering over scientific figures. The SciVQA corpus contains 3,000 real-world images of figures from scholarly publications [5], [6] in computational linguistics, natural language processing (NLP), and computer science. Each figure is annotated with seven closed-ended question-answer (QA) pairs focusing on visual and non-visual attributes. The dataset was developed using a semi-automatic pipeline, involving synthetic QA pairs generation with the Gemini 1.5-flash model⁴ and subsequent validation by experts from DFKI. The objective of this initiative is to establish a benchmark for evaluating the efficiency of multimodal large language models (MLLMs) in QA over scientific figures. The dataset is used in the SciVQA shared task,⁵ which is currently running under the umbrella of the Scholarly Document Processing workshop,⁶ organized as part of the ACL 2025 conference.⁷ This speedboat opens the field of visual QA to researchers in their daily information needs.

As can be seen, we run these speedboat projects to enter new research fields or to speed up the research process itself. Our aim is to showcase the transformational potential of AI and the variety of possible research pathways ahead.

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⁴<https://deepmind.google/technologies/gemini/flash/>

⁵<https://sdproc.org/2025/scivqa.html>

⁶<https://sdproc.org/2025/index.html>

⁷<https://2025.aclweb.org/>